

A Study on Influences of Organizational Culture at Golden Cashew Products, Pondicherry

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study is to provide an impact over the organizational culture experienced by the employees. Organizational culture is a set of attitude and behavior adopted by the employees in the organization by various situations. Job satisfactions are related to the perceptions of their working environment. The main objective of the study is to find the significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction. Also, to retain the talented and efficient workforce in the organization and also to improve the organizational growth and environment. The study employed with stratified random sampling method. This research work is a survey to make use of sample about 80 employees drawn from the population of 100 employees. The major source of data used in this study is primary data and secondary data is collected by using questionnaire method. The research observed in the study is, there is no significant difference between the organizational culture and the job satisfaction. It is concluded that the employee job satisfaction did not play any role on how they worked in the culture that was followed by the organization.

KEYWORDS: Organizational culture, Job satisfaction, Workforce, Attitude and Behavior

INTRODUCTION

The organizational culture as a uniform perception based on organization which has common characteristics. Organizational culture, according to the author is something descriptive and effectively it can distinguish one particular organization from another. It can also integrate individuals and groups of organization systems. (Robbins, 2007)

It is a common belief and concept that create the psychological and social environment to the employees in the organization. In other words the business environment plays unique characteristics in the company culture often contributes to its success that cannot be adopted by our competitors. A strong organizational culture encourages the employees to avoid absenteeism and also committed their work with value and belief followed by the organization. It is also known as corporate culture; it has a basic assumption and values with intangible strategies which defines the behavior, operation, and activities followed by the organization. To put it in another way it has a general attitude, mood and motivation through reward or lack of employees in the organization.

Job satisfaction is an as attitude which results from the balancing and summation of many specific likes and dislikes experienced in connection with the job. (Bullock 1952)

Job satisfaction is a worker based achievement and success

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of the job. Job satisfaction is directly connected to the productivity improvement of the organization. It is a key factor to influencing the employee to recognize, income, promotion to achieve their individual as well as organizational goal.

The importance of organizational culture is to provide unity, loyalty, coordination, direction and identity between the employees to complete their job in a timely manner and it will motivate the employees in the positive way improve the organizational productivity.

The factors influencing organizational culture are:

1. Team Work
2. Involvement
3. Control and Coordination
4. Communication and
5. Rewards and Incentives

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Organizational culture is mostly invisible to the members of the organization or external environment (Ion Alexandru, 2015), the organizational culture characteristics and importance that assist in promoting a healthy and successful organization. Values of culture that help shape organizational success and statute are discussed in addition to how the culture can change the way of activity evolution.

“The only thing of real importance that leaders do is to create and manage culture.” “If you do not manage culture, it manages you, and you may not even be aware of the extent to which this is happening.” (Edgar Schein).

Organizational development has some particular features that can increase sustainability on basis of effectiveness. The enhancement in performance contributes to employee commitment while norms, values and objectives contribute in enhancing the culture of an organization (Awadh & Saad, 2013).

The organization culture has been coming to our research and practice in 1980s after experience management and scientific management (Kotter John P. & Heskett, 1992).

"Around here, nobody dares make waves" or, "Do just enough to get by and people will leave you alone," the organization's performance will reflect those beliefs. Moreover, if the cultural belief system contains positive approaches, such as, "Winners are rewarded here" or, "People really care if you do a good job in this outfit," that also will be reflected in the organization's performance (Ismael Younis Abu-Jarad, 2010).

Culture which is different from the material and technical elements that are visible is one of the factors that impact on the organizational performance, and play an influential role the same as above-mentioned elements. (ZHANG Ya-li, 2009)

Change is generally a response to some significant threat or opportunity arising outside of the organization (Gilgeous, 1997). Every organization or institution is itself based on its own rules, values, perceptions and beliefs by which they operate.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

This research intended to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify the factors influencing organizational culture at Golden cashews product Pondicherry.
2. To find the significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction
3. To find the significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of the respondents.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. H0: There is no significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction
Ha: There is a significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction

2. H0: There is no significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of the respondents.

Ha: There is a significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of the respondents.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is the art of scientific investigation and it is a systematic way to solving the problem, the theoretical analysis of procedure applied to the field of study (Kothari 2004). Research methodology will understand the science of studying how research is done systematically to solve the hypothetical procedure in the research field.

1. DATA TYPES:

In this study primary and secondary data is used. Primary data is a data which is collected fresh at first time by the researcher himself viva collecting questionnaire, observation method, telephone interview method and personal interview method. Secondary data is a data which is collected by someone else already like books, journals, articles etc.

2. SAMPLING METHOD:

In this study stratified random sampling method is used. In this method the population is divided into various subpopulations. In the survey the population is varies then the subpopulation then we select items from each stratum to constitute a sample.

3. TYPE OF RESEARCH:

The descriptive research is used in this study. The main characteristic of descriptive research as no control over the research variables, and without covering why it is occurs.

4. POPULATION:

The population is defined as a group of event or things of interest that the researcher wishes to investigate. In this study the population is finite and the sample N=100 and the sample size n=80 (permanent staff are 12 and the contract employees are 68).

5. STATISTICAL TOOLS:

To make an effective recharge the following tools are used:

- Percentage method
- Bar chart
- Chi-square method
- ANOVA

DATA INTERPRETATION

Table1. Demographic variables of the respondent

Demographic profile		Frequency	Percentage
Age of the employee	Below 25	38	48
	26-30	21	26
	31-35	16	20
	36-40	5	6
Educational Qualification	UG	14	18
	PG	0	0
	Diploma	66	82
Gender	Male	45	56
	Female	35	44

SOURCE: Primary data

From the above table1 it is shows that 48% of the respondents are in the age group of below 25 years, 26% of the respondents are in the age group of 26-30 and 20% of the respondents are in the age group of 31-35 and 6% of the respondents are in the age group of 36-40 in our organization under age category. Educational Qualification of the respondents is shows that 82% of the respondents are diploma, 18 %of the respondents are undergraduates under the educational qualification category. Gender of the respondents is shows that there is 56 % of male and 44% of female employees in our organization.

Table2 Factors influencing organizational culture

Factor	Maximum score	Actual score
Team work	1600	1346
Involvement	1600	1276
Control and Coordination	1600	1297
Communications	1600	1344
Rewards and incentives	1600	1358

SOURCE: Primary data

From the above table 2 it was found that the most influencing factor of Organizational culture at Golden Cashews product, Pondicherry is rewards and incentives.

Table3 Chi square test

H0: There is no significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of the respondents.

ATTRIBUTES	AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE				
Low	0	0	0	0
Moderate	1	1	0	2
High	57	21	0	78
Total	58	22	0	80

SOURCE: Primary data

From the chi square table 3 it is infer that the result shows P-value is 0.97 which is greater than 0.05 and the degrees of freedom 4. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It is found that there is no significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of the respondents.

Table4 Analysis of Variance of Organizational Culture

H0: There is no significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

SOURCE OF VARIATION	SUM OF SQUARE	DEGREE OF FREEDOM	MEAN SQUARE	F-VALUE	P- VALUE
BETWEEN GROUPS	833.5556	2	416.7778	0.82007	0.484339
WITHIN GROUPS	3049.333	6	508.2222		
TOTAL	3882.889	8			

SOURCE: Primary data

From the above table 4 it is found that p-value is 0.4843 which is greater than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It is found that there is no significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

FINDINGS

1. The most influencing factor of organizational culture at Golden cashew Products. Puducherry was rewards and incentives.
2. It was found that by using Chi-Square test P-value is 0.97 which was greater than 0.05 and there is no significant association between organizational culture and age wise classification of employees.
3. By using ANOVA it is found that the p-value for job satisfaction and organizational culture is 0.4843 which is greater than 0.05. It was found that there is no significant difference between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The company would maintain the team spirit among the employees can be encouraged by the supervisors and motivates the employees to satisfy their needs.
2. The employees would be appreciated to come up with the new innovative ideas to solve the problem that would arise in the future, and they are also trained to become proactive employees in the organization.
3. The supervisors allocating of work to the employees without any favoritism.
4. The employees should have certain level of freedom to plan and act in its own and also adhere to the supervisor’s instruction.
5. The top management recognizes the employees through reward system periodically.

CONCLUSION

It is evident from the study that a variety of factors influencing the organizational culture and the job satisfaction. The Organization culture is a set of assumptions that can be used to guide the employee's appropriate behavior in various situations. It is also significant to discover that there is direct and positive relationship between the Organizational culture and the Job satisfaction.

The study that was concludes by using Chi Square test that there is no significant association between the organizational culture and the age wise classification of the employee in the organization. The result clearly shows that the age of the employee does not play any role on how they worked in the culture that they are followed in the organization.

By using ANOVA it was conclude that there is no significant relationship between the Organizational culture and the Job satisfaction of the employees in the Golden Cashew Product, Pondicherry.

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